

Suggested format for a conversation on Repeatability Across Generations

A guide for conversation leaders and local organisers

This is a suggested way of leading a conversation about the document *Repeatability Across Generations* and the questions it raises.

The document is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18236660>

The purpose is not to work through the document page by page. The document is used as a starting point for conversation. The person leading the conversation keeps the meeting together and makes sure that everyone who wants to speak has the opportunity to do so. The participants shape the content through the questions, experiences and objections they choose to raise.

The questions do not need to be formulated in advance. They can emerge from the participants' own experiences, questions and objections, and during the course of the conversation.

The organiser should make sure that coffee or tea is available during the break.

1. If there are more than 15–20 participants, divide the meeting into two conversation groups

A group should preferably not be larger than 15–20 people.

2. A few introductory words from the person leading the conversation

Say a few words about who is organising the meeting, why it has been arranged, how long it is expected to last, whether there will be a break, and any other practical matters.

It is also useful to explain the basic structure of the meeting.

Remind participants that the conversation will be shaped by what they themselves choose to raise.

3. Set out a few simple meeting rules

The person leading the conversation may briefly set out a few simple rules for the meeting. The rules are not meant to limit what participants may think or say, but to make it possible to have a good conversation even when views differ.

Possible meeting rules:

- Speak briefly enough for others to take part.
- Listen without interrupting.
- Disagree with arguments, not with people.
- Ask questions when something is unclear.
- The aim is not to win a debate, but to explore the questions together.
- Help make it possible for different views to be heard.

4. Round of introductions

Each participant briefly introduces themselves with their name and, if they wish, says something about their expectations for the meeting.

5. A few minutes of individual reflection

Each participant takes a few minutes to think about what they would like to raise in the conversation.

It may be a fact, claim, argument, line of reasoning, proposal or matter of principle in the document — or something that seemed to be missing.

6. Talk in pairs or small groups

Let participants discuss the thoughts the document raised, two and two, or three and three depending on the number of participants.

Give this part enough time. Do not interrupt too early. Step in only if the conversation has clearly stopped or if a long time has passed.

If a pair or group does not get started, help them with a simple question:

- What was most important in the text?
- Was there anything you reacted to?
- Was there anything that felt useful?
- Was there anything you did not agree with?

7. Start the discussion with reports from the pairs or small groups

Let one pair or small group at a time briefly say what they discussed.

Ask each pair or group to raise no more than one question or theme at a time. The floor is then open for comments, questions and views from the other participants.

The task of the conversation leader is to keep the meeting focused on the question being discussed and to make sure that everyone who wants to speak has the opportunity to do so. When the question has been discussed enough, move on to the next pair or group.

When all pairs or groups have reported back, you can do another round if there is time before the break.

If the conversation slows down, the discussion questions at the end of this document can be used.

8. Continue the discussion until all pairs or groups have reported back

This may take between one and two hours, depending on the number of participants and the character of the conversation.

9. Coffee break and a chance to stretch — 15–20 minutes

Do not rush this part. Let people talk and find one another.

Some of the most interesting questions may well come up during the break, when people relax and no longer have everyone's attention on them.

10. Regather after the break

Ask whether anyone would like to bring up something that was discussed during the break, or anything else that should be raised.

11. Summary and closing round — allow 15–20 minutes

Invite each participant, in turn, to say briefly:

- What do I take with me from this meeting?
- Would it be meaningful to meet again?

12. If all or some of the participants want to meet again

In that case, agree on the purpose and theme, as well as the day, time and place.

The questions at the end of this document may help the group choose a theme.

13. Record contact details only if needed

If names or contact details are collected, be clear about why the information is being collected.

14. Close simply

Thank the participants.

Remind them where the document can be read or downloaded.

Tips for the person leading the conversation

- Do not rush the conversation. Allow enough time for people to think and respond.
- Treat the document as a basis for conversation, not as something participants have to agree with.
- Use open questions rather than yes-or-no questions.
- Help make room for everyone who wants to speak.
- It is also acceptable simply to listen.
- Remind participants, if needed, that the aim is not to win a debate, but to explore the questions together.
- Welcome objections. They can make the conversation better.
- Help the group keep the main question in view.
- If needed, remind the group that places, water, landscapes, everyday living conditions and people's own experiences are not side issues, but part of the sustainability question itself.
- If the conversation becomes too abstract, bring it back to concrete questions: land, water, landscapes, waste, responsibility, decisions and long-term consequences.
- If the conversation stays only with the local case, use the larger questions raised by the document to help the group see the wider context: energy systems, mineral flows, company law, corporate responsibility, EU policy and society's long-term choices.
- If the group wants to continue meeting, make sure there is a shared understanding of what the next step will be.

Questions to use if the conversation slows down

Repeatability, technology and sufficiency

- What does it mean for a project, an energy system or an infrastructure to be sustained, maintained and repeated across generations?
- Can a project be justified in terms of climate policy and still be unsustainable in the longer term?
- Does technology neutrality mean treating all technologies equally at the outset, or testing them all equally rigorously against long-term viability?
- What should be left undisturbed, and what do restraint or sufficiency mean in practice?

Place, local knowledge and decision-making

- What kind of society, living conditions and ways of life should be defended, preserved and maintained?
- What knowledge of the place exists among those who live there, work the land, depend on the water and live with the consequences of the decisions?
- Who should have the power to decide when projects affect land, water, landscapes and local communities over a long period of time?
- What does binding local influence mean when land, water and living environments are at stake?

Companies, law and responsibility

- What rules or frameworks are needed so that company management and boards are not guided solely by profit when land, water and local communities are at stake?
- Can company law, including the Companies Act, be understood as a kind of social experiment, where economic risk is limited while ecological and social consequences often fall outside the company's responsibility?
- What changes in law would be needed so that the environment, climate, biodiversity and long-term viability carry at least as much weight as shareholders' interest in profit?

Waste, mining, oil and system scale

- What generates the two major waste flows: atmospheric waste and geological waste?
- What, and in what quantities, does a mine actually produce: metals, raw materials, waste, risks, jobs, profits, landscape transformation — or all of these at the same time?
- What do we actually get from oil: energy, fuels, plastics, chemicals, fertilisers, asphalt and industrial raw materials — and what does this mean for the idea of a simple transition from fossil energy to electrification?
- Is the problem mainly which energy source we use, or also the scale, speed and material demands of society's total system?